

Implementing low traffic neighbourhoods to the expansion of cycle networks

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Summary

Low Traffic Neighbourhoods (LTNs) offer an opportunity to expand urban cycling networks effectively by routing cyclists through existing low stress streets. However, cycling networks in the UK remain disjointed, and LTNs are typically not used for city-wide network planning. To address this gap, we propose methods to compare cycling network growth strategies which incorporate LTNs. We study a scenario where LTNs are neglected, one where existing LTNs are considered, and one where additional LTNs are introduced. Applying our method to the Tyne & Wear metropolitan region, we find that strategies which prioritise the connections between LTNs create networks at a lower initial investment cost, whilst becoming less fragmented and better connected when compared to other approaches.

KEYWORDS: Low Traffic Neighbourhoods, Cycle Networks, Transport Planning, Open-source

1 Introduction: Cycle infrastructure and cycle network planning

Cycling is seeing increased attention from planners and governments globally as cities attempt to reduce pollution from daily transportation, whilst bolstering public health and social interactions (Cunha and Silva, 2023; Chapman et al., 2018; Brand et al., 2022). However, in comparison to many of its geographic neighbourhoods (Wardlaw, 2014; Pucher and Buehler, 2008), the United Kingdom lags significantly behind in terms of the cycling rate. A significant role in this difference is due to the lack of connected cycling infrastructure across UK cities (Aldred, 2012; Aldred et al., 2019), which broadly comes from a neglect of funding. Safe, cohesive and well connected infrastructure is

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shown to be related to higher cycling rates (Buehler and Dill, 2015; Paulsen and Rich, 2023), and thus can be targeted UK cities to improve the level of cycling. However, whilst the cost of cycle infrastructure remains low in comparison to vehicular roads there is typically far less resource to be spent. It is therefore important to consider; how can cycle infrastructure be improved in a cost effective yet cohesive manor.

Whilst segregated infrastructure is understood to provide the highest level of safety and comfort to cyclists (and thus prompts a high level of cycling), supplementary streets of low traffic stress are also understood to be beneficial for a cycling city (Imani et al., 2019). Within the UK, many neighbourhoods within cities already provide low traffic streets in the form of Low Traffic Neighbourhoods (LTNs) (Lavery et al., 2021; Larkin et al., 2025). These are residential areas of the city with reduced through-traffic, typically created through modal filtering, which remain permeable for cyclists. These streets, if correctly utilised, could provide many kilometres of safe cycling without the need for any extra investment, if connected to correctly.

This paper seeks to propose methods to plan cycle networks which include LTNs, in order to investigate if using LTNs within the cycle network design process can lead to better cycle networks for both the investor and the cyclist.

2 Methods: An algorithmic approach to connect cycling infrastructure

2.1 Input Data and Scenarios

Street networks are accessed from OpenStreetMap (OSM), using OSMNx (Boeing, 2017; OpenStreetMap contributors, 2024). From these street networks we obtain a network composed solely of protected cycle infrastructure to act as the bike network, and a fully bikeable network composed of all streets which can be cycled on.

Low Traffic Neighbourhoods are also derived from OSM, using the analysis methodology set out in Larkin et al. (2025). This provides polygons of neighbourhoods which can be plausibly be deemed as LTNs. To demonstrate the value of LTNs in the cycle network planning process, we create three scenarios of LTNs:

1. The No-LTN Scenario - where no LTNs are considered
2. The Current-LTN Scenario - a plausible estimation of the current number of LTNs within a city
3. The Double-LTN Scenario - a hypothetical scenario of if significantly more LTNs were introduced to a city

2.2 Network Preparation

The segregated cycling network used in this study is comprised only of infrastructure which separates cyclists from vehicular traffic, with the sole exception of streets within LTNs, which are deemed cycleable given the very low traffic volume and speed restrictions of 20 mph, in line with the safety literature on bicycle separation (CROW, 2016; Teschke et al., 2012; Buehler and Dill, 2015).

Table 1: Level of Stress Calculation

Cycle facility type from OSM	Level of Stress Classification
(Cycle) Path	1
Cycleway	1
Track	1
Bridleway	1
Living Street	2
Residential	2
Unclassified	3
Tertiary	3
Secondary	4
Primary	4
Trunk	4
Motorway	4

Table 2: Level of Stress values assigned to OpenStreetMap Highway tags. This system of ranking follows the work of Wasserman et al. (2019).

Not all streets are equally suited to cycling on, regardless of level of separation from traffic. We consider this when routing our network, and when analysing the bikeability of the network (Section 2.4, 3.4). To better represent the route choices preferred by cyclists, we adjust edge weights based on OpenStreetMap tags, which we use to estimate level of stress for any given street (Table 2).

2.3 Seed Points

In order to determine where the cycle network should connect to and from, we extend the methods outlined by Szell et al. (2022) to generate a set of seed points. An initial set of seed points is generated from each LTN zone, snapped to the nearest street. For areas not in LTNs, a second set of seed points is generated using TessPy’s (Saki et al., 2022) hexagonal tessellation, with cell diameters of approximately 1 km. In order to best represent the geography of the area, the tessellation is constrained to urban areas by using the Global Urban Footprint dataset from DLR (Esch et al., 2018) as a bounding polygon (Figure 1).

From the tessellation, a seed point is snapped to the nearest section of the protected cycle network within the cell. For cells without protected cycle infrastructure, the centroid is snapped to the street with the highest stroke value within the cell. The stroke value refers to the street with the highest continuous linearity, as calculated by Tripathy et al. (2020) and implemented in momepy (Fleischmann, 2019). This is used to ensure any future cycle infrastructure follows the logical path through a given area, as humans generally follow continuous streets in route finding (Manley et al., 2015).

Figure 1: Seed point generation workflow. Steps move from left to right. Blue points represent seed points within LTNs, red points represent seed points from the hexagonal tessellation.

2.4 Greedy Triangulation

With seed points set, greedy triangulation is employed to provide the connections (Szell et al., 2022; Folco et al., 2023), ensuring each seed point is connected in all directions (Figure 2). To determine the order of connections, five methods are employed and later compared:

- Edge Betweenness Centrality
- Potential Demand
- Random
- Edge Betweenness Centrality with LTNs prioritised
- Potential Demand with LTNs prioritised

Edge betweenness centrality (EBC) of links is used to identify the links most important to the network from a connectivity perspective, and thus as a proxy for demand across the city (Szell et al., 2022; Vybornova et al., 2022). The edge weight used in the EBC is calculated using the network length between any given points, minus the length of existing cycle infrastructure used in the lowest-cost path between these points. The edges are ranked by betweenness, with highest betweenness edges added first.

Potential Demand uses the estimated flow data from the “Go Dutch” scenario from the Propensity to Cycle Tool Lovelace et al. (2017) to assign a demand value along links. Links are ordered by highest demand.

Methods where LTNs are prioritised rank the connections between LTNs separately, and a manually ranked above any other connection. This is done to test the importance of the connections between LTNs, as it is hypothesised that there is potential to use connections between LTNs as a relative “quick win” in size and cost of cycle network expansion.

Random ordering is used to provide a baseline of the worst case scenario of planning.

Links between seed points are added to the solution under a budget of 1% of the full network size per iteration.

Figure 2: Edge betweenness on a fully connected greedy triangulation, using all seed points. Betweenness is calculated using the "on the ground" routed distance between seed point as the edge weighting to reflect the distance a cyclist would travel between any given pair of points.

3 Initial Highlight Results and Discussion

All results at this stage are preliminary and will be subject to future revisions. We present results for the Tyne & Wear region of North East England, UK. This comprises of five Local Authority Districts. Cycle networks are grown for each district separately, and results combined to produce average values.

3.1 Investment Distance

Investment length describes the amount of new infrastructure required to provide a connection between seed point pairs. We find that the initial cost of connections (cost referring to distance, rather than monetary) is greatly reduced by prioritising the LTNs. Compared to the baseline, the difference in distance can be over 3 km less for a network of the same size (Figure 3).

3.2 Network components

Whilst a cheaper network benefits the investor, the usefulness of the network is essential for the user (cyclists). The largest connect component size indicates how far a cyclist can maximally travel on the network. Again we find prioritising LTNs in the initial stages of investment provides a larger network for the cyclist, although standard EBC also perform well initially (Figure 4).

A similar trend is observed when look at how fragmented the cycling network is measuring the number of disconnected components of cycle infrastructure (Figure 5). We observe the the non-LTN-priority methods lag behind even the baseline average after the first 20 iterations, which is

Figure 3: Investment distance required at each stage of growth, shown as the deviation from the random growth baseline.

Figure 4: Size of the largest connected component, shown as the deviation from the random growth baseline.

Figure 5: Number of disconnected components at each stage of growth.

Mean	Maximum	Minimum
2.5%	3.6%	1.1%
9.6km	14.4km	5.8km

Table 3: Redundancy comparison between a scenario of no LTNs during network planning and the current scenario of LTNs.

also the stage where LTN-prioritised methods perform best.

3.3 Redundancy

To compare the potential redundancy of built cycle networks when considering increasing numbers of LTNs, we show the redundancy between networks. Comparing between the No-LTN scenario and current we find small but consistent levels of redundancy (Tables 3, 4). Since LTNs only cover a small portion of the city, and routes on protected infrastructure may already pass by LTNs, we do not expect huge redundancy values.

3.4 Bikeable Trips

A forthcoming addition to our methodology is a metric that allows us to integrate in our evaluation the *bikeability* of overall trips, based on the demand data from the "Go Dutch" scenario from the Propensity to Cycle Tool (Lovelace et al., 2017). So far, we experimented with approaches that (1) define as bikeable trips whose average level of traffic stress, weighted by edge length and trip

Mean	Maximum	Minimum
3.2%	5.5%	1.5%
11	20.4	6.9

Table 4: Redundancy comparison between a scenario of no LTNs during network planning and the current scenario of LTNs.

length, lies beneath a given threshold; (2) define trips as bikeable if and when both origin and destination come to lie on the same connected network component of bicycle infrastructure. Since the operationalisation of bikeability is not a straightforward task (Ahmed et al., 2024), we will be seeking feedback from the GISRUK community specifically on our computational methodology for this part of the work.

4 Conclusion

To explore how cycle networks can be planned more effectively through use of LTNs, we propose several methods to create network growth plans at the city scale. Using network metrics at each stage of growth across five growth approaches, we analyse the Tyne & Wear urban area in the UK. We find that approaches which prioritise the connections between LTNs provide best performance, particularly during the initial approximately 40% of connections being added.

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6 Biography

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Craig Robson (he/him) is a Lecturer in Data Centric Engineering at Newcastle University researching geospatial data science for exploring the impact of climate change.

Alistair Ford (he/him) is Senior Lecturer in Geospatial Data Analytics and School X Climate Fellow at Newcastle University researching spatial analysis within GIS for assessments of climate change impacts and land-use change.

Michael Szell (he/him) is an Associate Professor at NERDS (ITU Copenhagen) researching sustainable mobility and bicycle networks through network analysis, data science, and data visualization.

References

- Ahmed, T., Pirdavani, A., Wets, G., & Janssens, D. (2024). Bicycle infrastructure design principles in urban bikeability indices: A systematic review. *Sustainability*, *16*, <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU16062545> <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/16/6/2545>.
- Aldred, R. (2012). Governing transport from welfare state to hollow state: The case of cycling in the uk. *Transport Policy*, *23*, 95–102, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TRANPOL.2012.05.012>.
- Aldred, R., Watson, T., Lovelace, R., & Woodcock, J. (2019). Barriers to investing in cycling: Stakeholder views from england. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, *128*, 149–159, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TRA.2017.11.003>.
- Boeing, G. (2017). Osmnx: New methods for acquiring, constructing, analyzing, and visualizing complex street networks. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, *65*, 126–139, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2017.05.004>.
- Brand, C., Dekker, H. J., & Behrendt, F. (2022). Cycling, climate change and air pollution. *Advances in Transport Policy and Planning*, *10*, 235–264, <https://doi.org/10.1016/BS.ATPP.2022.04.010>.
- Buehler, R. & Dill, J. (2015). Bikeway networks: A review of effects on cycling. *Transport Reviews*, <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2015.1069908>.
- Chapman, R., Keall, M., Howden-Chapman, P., Grams, M., Witten, K., Randal, E., & Woodward, A. (2018). A cost benefit analysis of an active travel intervention with health and carbon emission reduction benefits. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health Article*, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15050962> www.mdpi.com/journal/ijerph.
- CROW (2016). *Design Manual for Bicycle Traffic*. Ede, The Netherlands: CROW.
- Cunha, I. & Silva, C. (2023). Equity impacts of cycling: examining the spatial-social distribution of bicycle-related benefits. *International Journal of Sustainable Transportation*, *17*, 573–591, <https://doi.org/10.1080/15568318.2022.2082343> <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/15568318.2022.2082343>.
- Esch, T., et al. (2018). Where we live — a summary of the achievements and planned evolution of the global urban footprint. *Remote Sensing 2018, Vol. 10, Page 895, 10*, 895, <https://doi.org/10.3390/RS10060895>.
- Fleischmann, M. (2019). momepy: Urban morphology measuring toolkit. *Journal of Open Source Software*, *4*, 1807, <https://doi.org/10.21105/JOSS.01807>.
- Folco, P., Gauvin, L., Tizzoni, M., & Szell, M. (2023). Data-driven micromobility network planning for demand and safety. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, *50*, 2087–2102, <https://doi.org/10.1177/23998083221135611/>.

- Imani, A. F., Miller, E. J., & Saxe, S. (2019). Cycle accessibility and level of traffic stress: A case study of Toronto. *Journal of Transport Geography*, *80*, 102496, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JTRANGE0.2019.102496>.
- Larkin, C., Robson, C., & Ford, A. (2025). Identification of plausible low traffic neighbourhoods using open data. *Journal of Cycling and Micromobility Research*, *6*, 100097, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCMR.2025.100097>.
- Laverty, A., Aldred, R., & Goodman, A. (2021). The impact of introducing low traffic neighbourhoods on road traffic injuries. *Findings, 2021*, <https://doi.org/10.32866/001C.18330>.
- Lovelace, R., Goodman, A., Aldred, R., Berkoff, N., Abbas, A., & Woodcock, J. (2017). The propensity to cycle tool: An open source online system for sustainable transport planning. *Journal of Transport and Land Use*, *10*, <https://doi.org/10.5198/jtlu.2016.862>.
- Manley, E. J., Orr, S. W., & Cheng, T. (2015). A heuristic model of bounded route choice in urban areas. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, *56*, 195–209, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TRC.2015.03.020>.
- OpenStreetMap contributors (2024). Openstreetmap. Accessed: 2024-11-25 <https://www.openstreetmap.org>.
- Paulsen, M. & Rich, J. (2023). Societally optimal expansion of bicycle networks. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, *174*, 102778, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TRB.2023.06.002>.
- Pucher, J. & Buehler, R. (2008). Making cycling irresistible: Lessons from the Netherlands, Denmark and Germany. *Transport Reviews*, <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441640701806612> <https://www.tandfonline.com/action/journalInformation?journalCode=ttrv20>.
- Saki, S., Hamann, J., & Hagen, T. (2022). Tesspy: a python package for geographical tessellation. *Journal of Open Source Software*, *7*, 4620, <https://doi.org/10.21105/JOSS.04620>.
- Szell, M., Mimar, S., Perlman, T., Ghoshal, G., & Sinatra, R. (2022). Growing urban bicycle networks. *Scientific Reports 2022 12:1*, *12*, 1–14, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-10783-y>.
- Teschke, K., et al. (2012). Route infrastructure and the risk of injuries to bicyclists: A case-crossover study. *American Journal of Public Health*, *102*, 2336–2343, <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2012.300762>.
- Tripathy, P., Rao, P., Balakrishnan, K., & Malladi, T. (2020). An open-source tool to extract natural continuity and hierarchy of urban street networks. *Urban Analytics and City Science*, *48*, 2188–2205, <https://doi.org/10.1177/2399808320967680>.
- Vybornova, A., Cunha, T., Gühneemann, A., & Szell, M. (2022). Automated detection of missing links in bicycle networks. *Geographical Analysis*, *55*, 239–267, <https://doi.org/10.1111/GEAN.12324>.

Wardlaw, M. J. (2014). History, risk, infrastructure: Perspectives on bicycling in the netherlands and the uk. *Journal of Transport and Health*, 1, 243–250, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JTH.2014.09.015>.

Wasserman, D., Rixey, A., Zhou, X. E., Levitt, D., & Benjamin, M. (2019). Evaluating open-streetmap's performance potential for level of traffic stress analysis. *Transportation Research Record*, 2673, 284–294, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0361198119836772/>.